

Studies on Extractive Determination of Copper(II) from some Vegetable Samples with Lead Diethyldithiocarbamate in Chloroform by Standard Addition Method

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In order to determine the amount of copper(II) from vegetable samples, the present work describes a method of extractive estimation of copper(II) from some vegetable samples by standard addition method using lead diethyldithiocarbamate in chloroform as extractant. The amount of copper(II) obtained from the samples was compared with that obtained by other methods.

Results and Discussion

The extraction of copper was observed to be maximum and remained practically constant between pH 2 and 3. For further studies, experiments were carried out at pH 2.5. The absorbances of different unknown ash solutions of fresh bean, white radish, tomato, green peas, cucumber and turnip were found to be 0.110, 0.072, 0.167, 0.190, 0.114 and 0.097 respectively. Addition of 2, 4, 6 and 8 μg of copper showed very good linear relationship between the absorbances and concentrations.

The results (Table 1) are in good agreement with each other. It is also revealed that fresh bean and green peas have high copper content. This amount of copper does not affect the health. This study throws some light on the amount of copper we consume per day per meal alongwith the vegetables.

TABLE 1—EXTRACTIVE ESTIMATION OF COPPER BY STANDARD ADDITION METHOD AND DITHIZONE METHOD

Sample	Copper found per 100 g of sample	
	Standard addition method* (μg)	Dithizone method** (μg)
Fresh bean (<i>Canavalia gladiata</i>)	87.9 \pm 2.0	82.2
White raddish (<i>Raphanus sativus</i>)	21.3 \pm 0.4	15.4
Tomato (<i>Lycopersicon esculentum</i>)	36.3 \pm 0.4	36.2
Green peas (<i>Pisum sativum</i>)	115.0 \pm 7.0	103.3
Cucumber (<i>Cucumis sativus</i>)	52.0 \pm 1.0	56.4
Turnip (<i>Brassica rapa</i>)	25.0 \pm 0.5	20.3

*Ref. 2. **Ref. 3.

Experimental

An Elico pH meter, Spectronic-20 (Bausch and Lomb) and Shimadzu spectrophotometer were used. The chemical used were of A.R. grade, unless otherwise specified. Commercial grade chloroform was purified¹ and distilled. The fraction collected at b.p. 60–61° was used as diluent for the extraction.

To a mixture of potassium nitrate solution (10%; 5 ml) and lead acetate solution (0.05 g in 10 ml water), was added diethyldithiocar-

bamate (0.1 g) followed by chloroform (100 ml). The mixture was shaken for 10 min and allowed to equilibrate. The chloroform layer was collected and diluted upto 250 ml with chloroform. Required amount of pentahydrated copper sulphate was dissolved in water and standardised. The desired metal ion concentration was prepared from this solution.

The vegetable samples such as fresh bean, white radish, tomato, green peas, cucumber and turnip were procured fresh from Nagpur local market in the month of January of the year. Each sample was cleaned and dried in an air-oven (90–100°) and subsequently dry-ashed in a muffle furnace (500–550°).

Sample of ash (1.0 g) was dissolved in aqua regia and heated to dryness. This procedure was repeated till the removal of all nitrate ions. It was diluted with 2 M HCl and filtered. The residue was thoroughly washed, and the washings and filtrate were diluted to 100 ml.

Eight systems were prepared each of which containing copper(II) (1.0 mg) and citric acid solution (10%; 5 ml). The pH of these systems was adjusted from 1 to 9. The volume of each system was kept constant (10 ml) with respective pH water. Copper(II) was extracted from each system with lead diethyldithiocarbamate solution in chloroform (5 ml). After drying, the absorbance of each extract was measured at 435 nm against lead diethyldithiocarbamate in chloroform.

Five systems were prepared containing constant amount of unknown and known amounts (0, 2, 4, 6 and 8 µg) of copper(II). To each system citric acid solution (5 ml; 10%) was added. The pH of the systems was adjusted to 2.5 and the volume kept constant (20 ml). Copper was extracted from each system with chloroform solution of lead diethyldithiocarbamate (2 × 5 ml). The absorbance of each extract was measured at 435 nm against the reagent blank.

Ash sample solution (5 ml) was extracted (2 × 5 ml) with 0.01% dithizone in carbontetrachloride solution. The extracts were collected together and the absorbance was measured at 515 nm against the reagent blank.

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